

IMPLEMENTATION OF PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING (PBL) APPROACH IN ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION AT THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

Dyah Ayu Pitaloka

dyhptlkaa@gmail.com

Abstract

This article discusses the problem-based learning (PBL) model in Islamic religious education at the senior high school level. The research questions addressed are: 1) What problems do students experience during the learning process? 2) How can the problems experienced by students during the learning process be solved? This article was written using problem-based learning research. Some of the problems experienced by high school students include a decline in interest in learning Islamic religious education, numerous distractions during learning, difficulty concentrating, and an inability to enjoy certain subjects. The solutions to overcome these problems include introducing Islam more deeply to students from an early age as a way to make religion the basis of everything, convincing students that learning religion is important as a way to avoid these problems, and parents must be able to show that worship is very important in Islam. Parents must also tell their children that worship is important and obligatory for Muslims by setting a good and proper example.

Keywords *Learning models, Problem-Based Learning Approach, and Islamic Religious Education.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a human need that cannot be separated from daily life. In the Indonesian dictionary, the word pendidikan (education) comes from the word “didik” (to educate) with the prefix ‘pe’ and the suffix “an,” which means the process or method of educating. Linguistically, the definition of education is the process of changing the attitudes and behavior of a person or group of people in an effort to mature humans through teaching and training (Mulyana et al., 2022). Education is guidance provided by adults for the development of children with the aim that children can sufficiently carry out their own life tasks independently without needing help from others. In other words, education is the preparation needed by humans to live their future lives (Agustina, Hamengkubuwono & Syahindra, 2020) . The purpose of education is also to make humans steadfast in themselves, pious and faithful to the commands of Allah SWT, have noble character, be intelligent, and be sensitive. Education is also capable of realizing or developing all the potential that exists within humans in the context of morality, diversity, individuality, and also society.

The educational problems faced in the current era cover several issues. A very important educational problem faced today is the low quality of education at every level, especially in primary and secondary education (Khalijah et al., 2022). These include a lack of access and facilities between urban and rural areas, inadequate infrastructure, low teacher quality, high education costs, and frequent changes to the Indonesian curriculum. Other problems can also come directly from students, such as low motivation and interest in learning. The low quality of student learning outcomes is caused by many factors. Dimiyati and Mudjiono identify two factors that influence learning outcomes, namely internal factors and external factors (Khalijah et al., 2022). However, Indonesia has now made some progress through its current curriculum, namely the independent curriculum. In this curriculum, Indonesia has made several improvements in the field of education that focus on essential material, character development through projects, and flexibility in teaching and preparing students with competencies, literacy, and the use of technology. This can help students to be more enthusiastic about learning.

One effort to increase student activity is by including problem-based learning modules, or what we call problem-based learning (PBL). This method requires students to think critically in solving problems they encounter. Of the several curricula in Indonesia, there is one curriculum that plays a very important role in developing students' critical thinking, namely the K13 curriculum. According to (Maro, 1981), the application of learning strategies in K-13 actually trains students to be able to think critically (critical thinking). Several literature sources say that Indonesian students lack critical thinking skills. The author found that the lack of critical thinking skills among students is caused by a 'generational culture' that cannot be easily eradicated. The application of learning strategies in K-13 trains students to think critically. Several literature also states that Indonesian students lack critical thinking skills. The author found that the lack of critical thinking skills among students is caused by a 'hereditary culture' that cannot be easily eradicated. Therefore, the application of this method is very appropriate because it uses real problems as learning materials. At this stage, teachers ensure that each issue raised is relevant to the basic competencies of PAI and is able to stimulate students' critical thinking skills. When learning begins, teachers orient students to the problem by presenting a case. As one component of Islamic education, the Islamic Religious Education learning method must contain the potential to direct the subject matter towards the Islamic religious education goals to be achieved through the learning process (Farida Isnaeni, 2016).

PROBLEM FORMULATION

In every learning process at school, there are bound to be some problems. In the Indonesian dictionary, the word “problematika” comes from the word “problem,” which means an issue or problem that arises. So, every learning process certainly has several issues that we face. It is also possible for these issues to arise in Islamic religious education lessons. These issues can hinder our learning process and also hinder the achievement of learning objectives, whether they originate from the environment, teachers, or students. These issues are as follows:

1. Decreased interest in learning Islamic education.

A decline in interest in learning also has a significant impact on learning. This is especially true if this decline in interest is in the area of religion, because religion is very important in every person's life. In order to see the results achieved by students, it is very important for us as teachers to observe every factor that affects each student. For example, we should observe student behavior during class and the level of discipline shown by each student in the classroom.

There are several factors that contribute to the lack of interest in education in high school, such as *First*, family relationships. This is caused by the way parents teach their children about religion in their daily lives. How parents show that worship is very important in Islam, parents must also tell their children that worship is important and obligatory for Muslims by setting a good and proper example. In this way, children will imitate what their parents do when they worship, because parents are role models for their children.

Second, the school environment. The school environment shapes students' personalities because it gives them the opportunity to adapt to everyday life at school. This factor is caused by social issues such as dating, bad company, and unfriendly friendships. Because of these problems, many students lose focus in their studies. Convincing students that religious studies are important is one way to avoid these problems.

Third, environmental factors at home or in the community. The community environment is a major factor in shaping students' personalities because it influences how they live their daily lives and how often they meet or interact with their home environment. These environmental factors have a significant impact on students, such as an unsupportive family or a lack of understanding of the importance of PAI in daily life. Introducing Islam more

deeply to students from an early age is also one way to do this, and making religion the basis of everything.

2. Numerous distractions during study time.

It is not uncommon for students to experience significant distractions that affect their focus during learning. Factors such as social media, television, and games can also cause significant distractions that affect students' concentration. Therefore, effective measures are needed to address this issue, such as making learning and study activities more exciting or limiting students' dependence on social media.

3. Students often have difficulty concentrating.

Concentration or focus is an issue that cannot be taken lightly. Difficulty concentrating can have a major impact on learning and can hinder students' learning. Here are some ways to avoid the concentration problems experienced by students:

a. Set goals to aim for or achieve

One reason students experience concentration or focus problems is that the tasks or workload they receive are too heavy, leaving them unsure of where to start. Taking on the easiest or simplest tasks is one way to overcome this problem. Students can structure their tasks and make learning easier this way.

b. Finding the right and enjoyable learning style

Every student has a very different learning style, so it is very important for them to find the right learning style. This is because everyone has a different learning style, such as learning individually or in groups. Therefore, students must be able to determine for themselves how they feel comfortable learning. This will allow them to stay focused on their lessons.

c. Don't push yourself too hard

Difficulty concentrating can also be caused by studying too hard or forcing yourself to think, thereby neglecting rest time, which can affect students' physical and mental health. The way to overcome this problem is to give ourselves enough rest time so that we can think again and concentrate better. It is also recommended that we accompany this with exercise and consume nutritious food and drinks.

4. Unable to enjoy certain subjects

Students often dislike certain subjects for various reasons, such as because they are not good at them, find them boring, believe that they are not very important, or because they dislike the teacher who teaches them. One way to overcome this problem is to give students a broader understanding of the future value of these subjects. Teachers should also help students discover why they should learn it, even if it is not relevant to their future career goals.

METHOD

The Problem-Based Learning model is a learning model that begins by presenting students with problems that are based on their daily experiences or experiences they have had in the past. Students then solve the problems to gain new knowledge. This is expected to enable students to learn knowledge related to the problem, while also developing problem-solving skills. (M. Taufiq Bawazier & Yuliastutik Yuliastutik, 2024). This research method and type examines how problem-based learning can be used to teach Islam in high schools. To achieve this goal, the problem-based learning approach was used as the research methodology. This method produced descriptive data in the form of behaviors and written or spoken words from the research subjects. To solve this problem, the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) Model became a reasonable and effective alternative to use. PBL is a student-centered or learner-centered learning approach. This approach begins learning by teaching students real and contextual problems. Students are trained to think critically, analytically, and solution-oriented during the process of problem identification, information search, discussion, argumentation, and conclusion drawing. The learning process in the classroom shows that teachers have implemented PBL systematically and structurally (Amirulloh et al., 2025).

Learning begins with orienting students to contextual problems that are relevant to everyday life. The learning process in the classroom shows that teachers have implemented PBL systematically and structurally. Learning begins with orienting students to contextual problems that are relevant to everyday life. Students are divided into PBL in PAI, allowing them to examine religious social phenomena more broadly. An example of PBL in Islamic religious education is as follows: The teacher presents a problem and then asks students to solve it in groups. For example, the teacher might

give the title “How can we overcome moral decadence and promiscuity among high school teenagers today by practicing the values of Sufi morals?”

The steps that students must take are:

- **Presentation of Issues:** Using news articles, case studies, or short videos, teachers present moral phenomena that occur among teenagers, such as bullying, gang fights, or excessive use of gadgets. Then, teachers create questions like the ones above for students to answer.
- **Group Organization:** Students are divided into several groups, each consisting of people.
- **Information Search:** Each group obtains information from various sources, such as the Qur'an, Hadith, books on morals, and relevant articles. They study Sufi concepts such as zuhud, wara', and tawakkal.
- **Group Discussion:** Groups discuss the information they have gathered. They look for connections between Sufi ethical concepts and solutions to moral decadence.
- **Developing Solutions:** Each group develops practical solutions to their problems. For example, they may create an ethical awareness campaign, a mentoring program, or a schedule of positive activities based on zuhud and tawakkal.
- **Solution Presentation:** Each group presents their discussion results and solutions in front of the class. Other groups can ask questions or provide feedback.
- **Reflection:** Students and teachers collaborate to reflect on the overall learning process, evaluate the available options, and strengthen their understanding of the importance of Sufi ethics in everyday life.

CONCLUSION

In Islamic Religious Education learning in high schools, the application of problem-based learning (PBL) has proven to be an effective approach to improving students' critical thinking skills. Students are encouraged to analyze, evaluate, and create solutions based on Islamic values through real-life problems related to everyday life. Compared to traditional lectures, this process makes learning more active, interactive, and meaningful. PBL can transform students into active learners who are directly involved in the learning process. Overall, the implementation of PBL in Islamic Education not only improves students' critical thinking skills, but also enriches their understanding of Islamic teachings in greater

depth. This model shapes a generation of Muslims who are not only intellectually intelligent, but also have strong character and are capable of problem solving.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Amirulloh, M. I., Habiburrohman, H., & El-Yunusi, M. Y. M. (2025). Penerapan Problem Based Learning: Pendekatan Inovatif untuk Peningkatan Hasil Belajar di Kelas. *Ngaos: Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Pembelajaran*, 3(1), 1–12.
<https://doi.org/10.59373/ngaos.v3i1.40>
- Farida Isnaeni, I. (2016). Model Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam Integratif. *FITRAH: Jurnal Kajian Ilmu-Ilmu Keislaman*, 2(1), 37–52.
<https://doi.org/10.24952/fitrah.v2i1.454>
- Khalijah, W. N., Jannah, M., Rehan, H. Z., Yohana, & Yohani. (2022). Peranan Metode Pembelajaran terhadap Minat dan Prestasi Belajar Al-Qur'an Hadis. *Al-Wasathiyah: Journal of Islamic Studies*, 2(2), 275–285. <https://doi.org/10.56672/xramch11>
- M. Taufiq Bawazier, & Yuliasutik Yuliasutik. (2024). Implementasi Model Pembelajaran Problem Based Learning Dalam Meningkatkan Motivasi Belajar Siswa Pada Mata Pelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam Di SMA Islam Perlaungan Waru Sidoarjo. *Jurnal Budi Pekerti Agama Islam*, 2(1), 135–149. <https://doi.org/10.61132/jbpai.v2i1.68>
- Maro, R. K. (1981). Strategi Pembelajaran K-13 Melatih Critical Thinking. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 53(9), 1689–1699.
- Mulyana, D., Sukandar, A., & Setiawan, M. (2022). Strategi Pembelajaran Guru Pendidikan Agama Islam dalam Meningkatkan Akhlakul Karimah Peserta Didik Di SMA IT Mekarjaya Garut. *Edunity Kajian Ilmu Sosial Dan Pendidikan*, 1(02), 49–54.
<https://doi.org/10.57096/edunity.v1i02.8>

